

0.078% total N. Available P, K, and Zn were 11.8 kg/ha, 368.5 kg/ha, and 1.68 kg/ha (DTPA extractable Zn). Soil CEC was 21.80 meq/100 g.

The trial was in a randomized block design with nine treatments and three replications.

All plots except control and urea

supergranule (USG) treatments received one basal application of 100 kg N/ha during puddling. USG was applied immediately before transplanting by pressing the granules below the surface soil with the foot.

Sulfur-coated urea (SCU) gave the

highest grain yield, N uptake, and fertilizer efficiency (see table). In our laboratory, bitumen is used to coat ureaform. Results are comparable to those with SCU. Ureaform formulations also showed a significant increase in fertilizer efficiency. □

Damaged seedling roots and grain yield

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We studied the effect of seedling root damage on grain yield during kharif 1985 and 1986. The treatments follow: roots were handled carefully to avoid injury, roots trimmed from the base, seedlings uprooted from semidry soil with the help of a spade.

Thirty-day-old Jaya seedlings were transplanted the first week of July and fertilized with 120-26-50-6 kg N-P-K-Zn/ha. All of the P, K, and Zn were applied basally at transplanting. N was applied in 3 equal splits: basal, 21 d after transplanting (DT) and 42 DT.

Experimental field was clay loam with pH 8.1, low N, and medium P and K.

Root injury did not affect grain yield (see table). In transplanting rice, uprooting seedlings with the help of a spade may minimize labor costs. □

Effect of root injury on grain yield, Kaul, India.

Treatment	Panicles (no./hill)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
All roots intact	10	120	5.6
Roots 100% cut	9.5	128	5.5
Seedlings uprooted with spade	10	125	5.7

Performance of long-duration CR1009 with aged seedlings

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In the Cauvery delta during Aug-Feb

(samba season), transplanting of widely cultivated 165-d duration CR 1009 is sometimes delayed because of delayed receipt of water in the canal. We tested the performance of late-planted CR1009 during 1985-86 samba. Seedlings were transplanted 30, 40, 50, and 60 d after

seeding.

Plant height, panicles/hill, panicle weight, grain weight/panicle, 100-grain weight, and grain yield were not affected by planting up to 50 d after sowing (see table). Later planting reduced yield parameters and yield. □

Performance of late-planted CR1009 in 1985-86 samba, Aduthurai, India.^a

Seedling age (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle weight (g)	Grain weight/panicle (g)	100-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
30	92 a	8.5 a	4.11 a	3.82 a	2.38 a	5.40 a
40	89 a	8.9 a	4.27 a	3.92 a	2.30 a	5.49 a
50	88 a	9.3 a	4.09 a	3.72 a	2.25 a	5.65 a
60	87 a	7.5 b	3.54 b	3.24 b	2.18 a	4.43 b

^aIn a column, numbers followed by a common letter are statistically identical at the 95% level of confidence.

Preservation of *Azolla pinnata* germplasm

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Senescence and death of azolla during the summer is common in tropical areas. We have developed a technique to preserve germplasm of *Azolla pinnata*.

Surface-sterilized fronds were inoculated on sterilized N-free medium solidified with 0.9% agar. Cultures were incubated at 25 ± 1°C and illuminated

with cool white fluorescent light for a 16/8 light/dark cycle.

Growth of azolla was extremely slow compared to growth in a liquid medium (see table). The fronds remained green for more than 3 mo and, when transferred to a N-free liquid medium, continued to grow and develop faster. Viability of the fronds transferred to liquid medium was 100%. The azolla cultures also were easy to transport. □

Growth of *Azolla pinnata* in solid and liquid medium. Baroda, India.

Period (wk)	Fresh weight (mg)	
	Solid medium	Liquid medium
0	300 ± 20.0	300 ± 20.0
1	398 ± 20.6	698 ± 29.8
2	518 ± 22.1	1258 ± 34.0
3	780 ± 39.1	2638 ± 73.2

Ammonia volatilization loss in rice soils of Cauvery Delta

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We quantified NH₃ loss using different sources of N with basal and split application of 90 kg N/ha in Jun-Sep 1984. Experimental field soil was a clay